

LITERARY TRANSLATION AND THE CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN THIS PROCESS: BASED ON ERKIN VOHIDOV'S POETRY

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the linguistic, cultural, and stylistic challenges in literary translation, analyzing them through the process of translating the poetry of renowned Uzbek poet Erkin Vohidov into English. Practical strategies such as contextual adaptation, semantic equivalence selection, and compensation techniques are emphasized as solutions.

Keywords: literary translation, lexical challenges, cultural terms, national metaphors, poetic style, equivalence, contextual adaptation.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is not merely converting one language into another, it is also a medium of communication between cultures. Literary translation, in particular, poses numerous lexical and grammatical challenges, as it must convey not only words but also poetic rhythm, national spirit, and the author's personal emotions and individuality. Lexical difficulties in literary translation primarily arise in the proper and natural rendering of metaphorical expressions, archaic or historical terms, dialect-specific words, and unique cultural concepts into another language. Therefore, a translator must go beyond linguistic competence and master the skill of effectively conveying meaning and emotions through appropriate artistic techniques.

When translating the poetry of one of the leading figures of Uzbek literature, Erkin Vohidov, similar literary and lexical challenges may arise. His works extensively incorporate folkloric expressions, national symbols, historical and religious imagery, and philosophical reflections. This makes the translation process particularly complex, especially in preserving the nuances of national and historical lexical units, metaphors, metonymies, idioms, as well as poetic form and rhythm. Additionally, each language's unique lexical and grammatical structures play a crucial role, as some Uzbek words and phrases may lack direct equivalents in English or carry different semantic connotations [1].

For instance, idiomatic expressions found in Erkin Vohidov's poetry, such as "ko'ngil ko'zi" ("the eye of the heart"), "uyg'oq yurak" ("the vigilant heart"), and "ishq daryosi" ("the river of love"), risk losing their poetic essence if translated literally. Therefore, the translator must ensure not only semantic and grammatical accuracy but

also stylistic and aesthetic appropriateness. Literary translation not only makes literary works accessible in different languages but also strives to preserve their artistic and aesthetic qualities. Hence, a translator must analyze the linguistic and contextual meanings of the text in depth and seek appropriate equivalent solutions [2].

Lexical challenges in literary translation generally stem from the following factors:

- Interlingual differences – Variations in lexical systems and semantic structures across languages.
- Cultural specificities – Unique cultural expressions and symbols that pose difficulties in translation.
- Poetic lexicon and metaphors – Poetic expressions, idioms, and symbols that may lose their artistic effect when translated.

These are among the primary challenges faced by literary translators, particularly in poetry translation. This study examines translation issues and solutions based on Erkin Vohidov's poetry, employing a comparative method to analyze similarities and differences between the original text and its translation.

By the 1960s, Erkin Vohidov played a significant role in revitalizing classical Uzbek prosody (aruz). According to A. Hojimatov, "In the poetry of the 1960s, aruz continued to serve as a transparent medium for reflecting the subtle and complex emotions of contemporary individuals". Thus, caution is necessary when translating poetic lines, as mistranslations or inappropriate word choices may diminish the impact of the translated work [3].

According to translation theory, it is essential to consider the semantic and structural characteristics of word combinations during translation. The primary recommendation is to first translate the noun, as adjectives and other modifiers serve to define it, and the noun carries the core meaning in a sentence. The next step for the translator is to identify semantic groups within the sentence, determine the type of grammatical relationships between adjectives and nouns, and apply the grammatical norms of the target language appropriately.

When addressing lexical challenges in Erkin Vohidov's poetry, it is important to recognize that his work is deeply intertwined with Uzbek national identity and historical consciousness. He skillfully integrates folklore, classical literature, and modern artistic thought into his poetry. Consequently, the following key lexical difficulties arise when translating his works:

National and historical lexical units: Vohidov frequently employs national, historical, archaic, and dialect-specific terms, such as:

"Bobolar ruhi" – "Ancestors' spirit" or "The spirit of forefathers"

"Ona zamin" – "Motherland" or "The sacred land"

A literal translation of such terms may strip them of their poetic essence, necessitating the search for alternative equivalent expressions that convey their intended meaning [4].

Vohidov's poetry reflects Uzbek cultural traditions, customs, and lifestyle. For instance, works like "Ona yurt" ("Motherland") and "Vatan sog'inchi" ("Longing for the Homeland") highlight national values, making cultural adaptation crucial in translation. When direct equivalents are unavailable, translators may employ the following strategies:

- Explanatory translation – Providing additional context or definitions for complex or unique terms.
- Transliteration – Retaining national words in their original form while offering explanations.
- Cultural substitution – Replacing a cultural element with a more familiar equivalent in the target language [6].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the primary lexical challenges in translating Erkin Vohidov's poetry into English arise from metaphors, national-cultural elements, and contextual differences. Effective translation strategies include selecting appropriate equivalents, contextual adaptation, and explanatory translation. Maintaining the author's style and artistic impact is essential in literary translation. Therefore, beyond linguistic knowledge, a deep understanding of cultural and artistic nuances is necessary. The findings of this study may provide both theoretical and practical insights for translators and philologists.

REFERENCES

1. Karimov N. Erkin Vohidov gulshani. To quyosh sochgayki nur. Erkin Vohidov hayoti va ijodi zamondoshlari nigohida. –Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2016.
2. Eshqobilova M.P. Erkin Vohidov publitsistikasing ijtimoiy-estetik mohiyati // Miasto Przyszłości Vol.45, 2024.–B130-133.
3. G'afurov.I. Mo'minov.O. N.Qahramonov. Tajima nazariyasi. – Toshkent: Tafakkur Bo'stoni, 2012.–197 b.
4. E. Vohidov "Muhabbat". Toshkent.G'. G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti.1976.
5. Vohidov E. Saylanma. Ikki jildlik. Birinchi jild. Muhabbatnoma. – Toshkent: G'.G'ulom nomidagi Adabiyot va san`at nashriyoti, 1986

